

The Effect of Service Quality and 7P Marketing Mix on Repurchase Intention with Customer Satisfaction as Intervening Variable (Study at Perihal Kopi)

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the relationship between service quality and 7P marketing mix as key factors in achieving customer satisfaction and repurchase intention. The focus is to measure the extent to which customer satisfaction can influence the desire to repurchase. Service quality and the 7P marketing mix are considered the main predictors of customer satisfaction that can be assessed directly through consumer perceptions. The study method involves analysing customer assessment of various aspects of service quality and 7P marketing mix at Perihal Kopi, Depok. This study was conducted quantitatively by distributing online questionnaires to 237 respondents around JABODETABEK with the main criteria of respondent is individual who has visited Perihal Kopi. Data analysis used are instrument validity and reliability test, hypothesis test, and path analysis using the SmartPLS 4 Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) program. The result of this study indicates all the items of each variable are valid and reliable. Based on the findings, service quality has no significant effect to customer satisfaction and repurchase intention while 7P marketing mix has a significant effect to customer satisfaction and repurchase intention. The results of this study are expected to provide a deep understanding of the Perihal Kopi's position from the customer's perspective, allowing the Perihal Kopi to identify the areas that need to be improved. By understanding the factors that affect customer satisfaction, Perihal Kopi can design and implement effective action plans to improve the 7P marketing mix and achieve repurchase intention goals in the future.

KEYWORDS: 7P Marketing Mix, Customer Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention, Service Quality.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, people are required to find strategies to survive and carry out their activities. The same with entrepreneurs must also run a business properly to be able to satisfy consumers because basically a business is formed in order to get the expected profit and maintain its market share. In this case, business, especially in the culinary industry who serve coffee products are one of the fastest growing businesses. Currently, coffee has become part of society in Indonesia and does not attract a certain group. From teenagers to the elderly, all began to consume coffee, which is not just to get rid of drowsiness, but drinking coffee has become part of the lifestyle (Kasali, 2010 in Wardhana, 2014). The coffee consumption in Indonesia is growing every year and is predicted to continue to increase until early 2022 with a growth in coffee consumption of 8.22% per year and keep going further. In addition to the development of coffee consumption in Indonesia which continues to increase, coffee shops in Indonesia are also experiencing increasing growth every year. The 2019 Annual Data on Indonesian Coffee Consumption issued by the Global Agricultural Information Network shows that the projected domestic consumption in 2019-2020 reached 294,000 tons, an increase of around 13.9% compared to consumption in 2018/2019 which reached 258,000 tons (Toffin, 2019). The spread of the coffee business in Indonesia is spreading not only in big cities, but even small towns have many coffee entrepreneurs who open coffee shops. According to one of the coffee shop owners in West Java, Irfan Rahadian (2019) said that the profit margin that coffee vendors can get is quite large. Especially if coffee shop entrepreneurs can get raw materials for coffee beans at low prices, such as from farmers directly. However, the coffee business opportunity in Indonesia, which was initially very convincing in early 2020, experienced the beginning of its dark period because with the discovery of the Covid-19 pandemic virus, this certainly had a very significant impact on all aspects of life and industry. Many changes have occurred due to government regulations enacted to minimize the spread of the outbreak. Many changes have occurred due to government regulations enacted to minimize the spread of the outbreak. One of them is company rules that implement "work from home". The presence of the "work from home" policy due to the covid-19 pandemic has drastically changed activity patterns, which are usually diverse and free, turning into monotonous and bound activity patterns. In the midst of boredom, saturation, and stress due to changing policies and activity patterns, many

people tend to look for a different atmosphere with the eventual emergence of the "work form cafe" phenomenon. On the other hand, the presence of this policy did not dampen the development of the food and beverages industry sector. This is evident that during 2021 – 2023, many newcomer entrepreneurs started their coffee shop business around the Depok. With the booming coffee shop business to date and to deal with post-pandemic consumer behavior, this is an attraction to conduct study on this issue where with so many competitors, what things should coffee shop business do to maintain business stability. Related to this, coffee shops need to build new business strategies to compete with their competitors and survive in this era.

A. Company Profile

Perihal Kopi has earned a unique place as the only coffee shop along Keadilan Raya Street, Sawangan, Depok, West Java. Since it was established in January 2020, Perihal Kopi has become a popular destination for coffee lovers in the Sawangan. At first, Perihal Kopi was operated in a small shophouse on the edge of Keadilan Raya Street No. 20, with the owner's main focus on selling coffee without any specific theme for the coffee shop. However, in middle of 2020, Perihal Kopi decided to move its location to Keadilan Raya Street No. 69, located behind the owner's home yard. This move allowed Perihal Kopi to adopt a new theme as an outdoor coffee shop. Perihal Kopi new location has a large space, with an area of about 500 squares. Since it's a hidden location makes the atmosphere at Perihal Kopi quiet and cozy, making it a prime destination for workers who want to work from a coffee shop in Depok, especially in the Sawangan area. Perihal Kopi has daily operating hours from 8am to 11pm. On weekends, Perihal Kopi attracts customers with live music performances held until closing. The name "Perihal Kopi" was chosen for a unique reason that the owner wanted this place to be an endless story about life. The main vision of Perihal Kopi vision is become a well-known comfortable place for chilling in Depok and creating new job opportunity for local human resources where the vision is creating a comfortable and welcoming atmosphere to relax, provide a high-quality services and product, and become a place that have a strong identity.

B. Business Issue

Perihal Kopi has faced interesting business dynamics since its establishment four months before the Covid-19 pandemic. In the first two quarters, Perihal Kopi's sales did not reach the desired target because it was still in the sales development stage. However, in the next quarter along with the move of Perihal Kopi's location, there was a sharp increase in sales where there was a factor of the implementation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions ("PSBB") which at that time prevented other places from opening until night. Perihal Kopi's new location was in the courtyard next to the owner's house, Perihal Kopi became an attractive destination because it was spacious, uncrowded, and slightly secluded from the highway. This made it possible for customers, who at the time could not gather elsewhere due to PSBB regulations, to gather at Perihal Kopi until midnight. However, since PSBB was abolished, Perihal Kopi's sales have started to decline coupled with the emergence of many competitors around Perihal Kopi. Many customers who were initially loyal to Perihal Kopi during the PSBB period not returned and are looking for other places to hang out, as the other places are now also allowed to open until night. Issues that arise are what causes customers not to return; whether this is due to factors of service quality provided by Perihal Kopi, because of marketing mix elements that may have contributed to the decline in sales, or other factors. To overcome this problem, Perihal Kopi needs to conduct an in-depth analysis of customer preferences, improve service quality, and consider innovative marketing strategies to face increasingly fierce competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Service Quality

According to Kotler and Keller (2020), service quality is flawless delivery of the ideal output for any service organization. Service quality according to experts refers to the comparison between customer expectations of the services provided and the actual performance of these services. In evaluating service quality can be done using the SERVQUAL scale, there are several dimensions in service quality, such as Reliability, where the company's ability to provide services as promised and handle problems efficiently. Responsiveness, where the company has willingness to help customers and provide prompt service. Assurance, where the knowledge of employees and their ability to convey a sense of trust to customers. Empathy, where there is special attention and care given to the customers. Tangible, which describes the physical facilities, equipment, materials used by the company, and also the appearance of employees. Physical facilities are the company's ability to show its existence to external parties.

B. 7P Marketing Mix

According to Kotler and Keller (2020) and developed by other studies, the 7P Marketing Mix is a marketing strategy model that is seven important elements that affect business success. Here are the seven elements of the 7P Marketing Mix:

- a. Product: Refers to products or services combination that are made to the target market and passed on to fulfill customer needs.
- b. Price: The price is the amount of money for the product or service offered by the company in accordance with the value provided and ensures the company's profit.
- c. Place: Company business activity that make the products or services available to reach targeted customers.
- d. Promotion: Activities that communicate the products and services to increase customer awareness and get customers to buy it which consists of five activities, (1) Advertising, (2) Sales promotion, (3) Publicity and (4) Public relations, and (5) Direct marketing.
- e. People: Human resources who have high skills and dedication to support business operations that are directly related to end customers and become the frontline in business activities.
- f. Physical Evidence: Providing tangible physical evidence to support customer purchases, such as stores, equipment, facilities, and after sales services.
- g. Process: The process system is an activity that shows how flow is provided to consumers while purchasing goods or services.

C. Customer Satisfaction

According to Kotler and Keller (2021) customer satisfaction is the extent to which a product's perceived performance matches a customer's expectations. If the performance of the product or service offered does not match customer expectations, customers tend to feel dissatisfied. If the performance of the product or service offered matches expectations, customers tend to feel satisfied. If the performance of the product or service offered exceeds expectations, customers tend to feel very satisfied or happy. Most studies show that higher levels of customer satisfaction led to greater customer loyalty, which in turn results in better company performance because customers tend to be return to buy products and services that match their expectations.

D. Repurchase Intention

According to Kotler and Keller (2021), repurchase intention is behavior that occurs in response to an object that shows the customer's desire to make a repurchase. Purchase intention occurs when consumers make a second or subsequent purchase, where the reason for the purchase is primarily triggered by the customer's experience with the product or service. The intention to repurchase is undoubtedly increased when the consumer feels satisfied and comfortable with the previous purchase and wants to reuse it (Savitri & Wardana, 2018).

STUDY MODEL

Based on the Figure 1, the hypothesis of this study are:

- H1: Service Quality has a positive relationship on Customer Satisfaction
H2: Marketing Mix has a positive relationship on Customer Satisfaction
H3: Customer Satisfaction has a positive relationship on Repurchase Intention
H4: Service Quality has positive relationship on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction
H5: Marketing Mix has positive relationship on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction

METHODOLOGY

According to Sugiyono (2018) quantitative data is a study method based on positivistic (concrete data), study data in the form of numbers that will be measured using statistics as a calculation test tool, related to the problem under study to produce a conclusion. In this study, authors used questionnaire to conduct customer survey which carried out through online questionnaire. The sample number needed for this survey calculated based on Malhotra (2006) that the sample size taken can be determined by multiplying the number of indicators by 5. In this study, the author uses 45 indicator questions from four variables with the number of samples $45 \times 5 = 200$ respondents. These total respondents can represent market share of Perihal Kopi who have bought and used the product and service in Perihal Kopi. The criteria for respondents are the use of a Likert scale worth 1-5. Likert scale describes the respondent's agreement or disagreement with the statements that will be given by the author. According to Supranto (2008), the values in the Likert scale can be explained as follows:

- 5 – Strongly Agree
- 4 – Agree
- 3 – Neutral
- 2 – Disagree
- 1 – Strongly Disagree

After getting the questionnaire results, the author will test the study instrument with Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis. PLS is a powerful analysis method which in this method is not based on many assumptions. In this study, the SEM-PLS method used is a reflective model which is usually used for testing study instruments model which is usually used for classical factor analysis (Chin, 1998). This study used SEM-PLS version 4 application to processing the data.

A. Measurement Model (Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, Construct Reliability and Validity)

Outer loadings factor value is a measure used to describes the magnitude of the correlation between each indicator measurement item and its variable. This can be done by calculating the standard loadings of the Outer loadings of each indicator, where the Outer loadings factor value of 0.7 can be said to be ideal, meaning that the indicator is said to be valid as an indicator to measure the variable. AVE is the average value of communality (mean of communalities or average communality). The communality of an indicator item is obtained from the root of the standardized outer loading value of the indicator which represents the variation in an item described from the construct. According to Hair, et al., 2011 quoted from (Pratama, 2017) states that AVE must be greater than 0.5. Cross loading is done to assess the discriminant validity of the indicator. An indicator is declared valid if the cross-loading value of the indicator on the associated construct (latent variable) is greater than the cross-loading on other constructs (latent variables). Composite Reliability value (ρ_c) is used to check and assess how well the indicators fit the variable and is a tool to measure the stability and internal consistency of the measurement model. In particular, Composite Reliability values of 0.60-0.70 are acceptable in exploratory study, while in more advanced stages of study, values between 0.70 and 0.90 can be considered satisfactory. Cronbach's alpha assumes that all indicators are equally reliable (i.e., all indicators have the same outer loadings on the construct). PLS-SEM prioritizes indicators according to their respective reliabilities.

B. Structural Model (R – Square Value, Q – Square Value, F – Square)

R square is a measure of the strength of the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable in linear regression. R square shows the percentage of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable. The R square value can range from 0 to 1. An R square value close to 1 indicates that the dependent variable can be explained well by the independent variable. Conversely, an R square value close to 0 indicates that the dependent variable cannot be explained well by the independent variables. Q – Square predictive relevance can measure the structural model, specifically how well the observed

values are generated by the model and its parameter estimates. A Q-Square value of 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance; conversely, if $Q\text{-Square} \leq 0$ indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. F-square test is conducted to determine the goodness of the model. The F-square value of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 can be interpreted whether the predictor of latent variables have a weak, medium, or large influence at the structural level (Ghozali, 2011).

C. Path Coefficient and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is using path analysis, so that the size of the hypothesis can be said to support or not can be seen from the relationship between the t-table and the t-statistic. The hypothesis supported if the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value. If the confidence level reaches 95%, then $\alpha = 0.05$ so that the t-table value = 1.96 is obtained, which means that the hypothesis is accepted if the significance value is >1.96 . If the significant value is >0.05 then the hypothesis is rejected which the regression coefficient is not significant. If the significant value is <0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted which regression coefficient is significant.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The analysis was conducted through questionnaires created using Google Forms, distributed both at Perihal Kopi's outlets and social media platforms. The distribution period for the questionnaires spanned from September to November 2023, allowing for a comprehensive collection of responses. The primary criterion for respondents to participate in the questionnaire was their status as individuals who have previously visited Perihal Kopi. Based on the questionnaire result, the total number of respondents taken in this study was 237 respondents. Of these, 200 of the respondents had visited Perihal Kopi, 37 respondents stated that they had never visited Perihal Kopi. The majority of respondents are male as much as 60.3%, while female respondents are 38.7%, with age range 14-25 years as much as 50.6%. Furthermore, followed by the most respondents from the age of 25 - 34 years which has a total percentage of 40.1%, and the age range of 35-44 years as much as 5.1% and respondents aged 35 years and over as much as 4.2%. Based on the questionnaire results, the occupation of respondent consists of 42.2% students, 36.7% private employees, and 8.9% fall into other job categories. From the questionnaire data, the 68.8% respondent came from Depok, 21.5% came from the Jakarta, Bogor, Tangerang, and Bekasi (JABOTABEK) area, and 9.7% came from other areas outside JABOTABEK.

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model

Service Quality variables are measured by fifteen statement indicators, Marketing Mix is measured by twenty-one statement indicators, Customer Satisfaction is measured by four statement indicators, and Repurchase Intention is measured by five question indicators. The criteria used in assessing the outer model are Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity and Composite Reliability.

Table 1. Evaluation of Measurement Model

Variable	Indicators	Loadings >0.70	Validity	AVE >0.5	Composite Reliability >0.70	Cronbach's Alpha >0.70	Cross Loading	Reliability
Service Quality (SQ)	SQ1	0,809	Valid	0,691	0,972	0,969	Valid	Reliable
	SQ2	0,773	Valid					
	SQ3	0,866	Valid					
	SQ4	0,887	Valid					
	SQ5	0,890	Valid					
	SQ6	0,862	Valid					
	SQ7	0,744	Valid					
	SQ8	0,884	Valid					
	SQ9	0,823	Valid					
	SQ10	0,845	Valid					
	SQ11	0,806	Valid					
	SQ12	0,838	Valid					
	SQ13	0,825	Valid					
	SQ14	0,824	Valid					
	SQ15	0,835	Valid					
Marketing Mix (MM)	MM1	0,819	Valid	0,699	0,980	0,978	Valid	Reliable
	MM2	0,882	Valid					
	MM3	0,773	Valid					
	MM4	0,811	Valid					
	MM5	0,900	Valid					
	MM6	0,890	Valid					
	MM7	0,732	Valid					
	MM8	0,730	Valid					
	MM9	0,837	Valid					
	MM10	0,760	Valid					
	MM11	0,750	Valid					
	MM12	0,873	Valid					
MM13	0,844	Valid						
MM14	0,871	Valid						
MM15	0,910	Valid						
MM16	0,880	Valid						
MM17	0,909	Valid						
MM18	0,879	Valid						
MM19	0,819	Valid						
MM20	0,816	Valid						
MM21	0,836	Valid						
Customer Satisfaction (CS)	CS1	0,893	Valid	0,856	0,960	0,944	Valid	Reliable
	CS2	0,944	Valid					
	CS3	0,946	Valid					
	CS4	0,917	Valid					
Repurchase Intention (RI)	RI1	0,822	Valid	0,736	0,933	0,910	Valid	Reliable
	RI2	0,883	Valid					
	RI3	0,894	Valid					
	RI4	0,900	Valid					
	RI5	0,785	Valid					

Convergent Validity

The convergent validity for each variable service quality, marketing mix, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention have outer loading value of > 0.70 so that the indicator is considered valid in measuring service quality, marketing mix, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention in this study. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value on the Service Quality variable is 0.697, which indicates that 69.7% of the information contained in the fifteen indicators can be reflected through the Service Quality variable, the

AVE value on the Marketing Mix variable is 0.699 which indicates that 69.9% of the information contained in the twenty-one can be reflected through the Marketing Mix variable, the AVE value on Customer Satisfaction is 0.856, which indicates that 85.6% of the information on the two indicators can be reflected through the Customer Satisfaction variable, and the AVE value of Repurchase Intention is 0.736, which indicates that 73.6% of the information contained in the five indicators can be reflected through Repurchase Intention.

Discriminant Validity

The second criterion used to evaluate the outer model is discriminant validity. The way to measure the outer model with discriminant validity includes based on the cross-loading value of the construct correlation with the measurement item being greater than the size of the other constructs, then this indicates that the latent constructs predict the size of their block better than the size of the other block. Based on the result, that value construct of the construct correlation with the measurement item being greater than the size of the other constructs. If the cross loading between the indicator and its construct is higher than other constructs, it means that the indicator can distinguish the construct it measures from other constructs. This indicates that the indicators of each variables have good discriminant validity.

Construct Reliability and Validity

To measure the reliability of a construct with formative indicators, it can be done in two ways, with Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha. An assessment that can be used to assess construct reliability and is declared reliable if the Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha values are above 0.70 for confirmatory study and 0.60-0.70 is still acceptable for exploratory study. Construct reliability in PLS reliability test is measured by criteria, namely Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha from the indicator block that measures the construct. The construct is declared reliable if the Composite Reliability value is greater than 0.70 while some restrictions on the Cronbach Alpha score are greater than 0.60. The Composite Reliability (CR) value of service quality is 0.972 and Cronbach Alpha (CA) is 0.969, which means higher than 0.70. This shows that indicators 1-15 have consistency in measuring Service Quality in Perihal Kopi. CR value of Marketing Mix is 0.980 and CA is 0.978, which means higher than 0.70. This shows that indicators 1-21 have consistency in measuring Marketing Mix in Perihal Kopi. The CR value of customer satisfaction is 0.960 and CA is 0.944, which means higher than 0.7, this shows that all indicators have consistency in measuring the Customer Satisfaction variable, and the CR value is 0.933 and CA is 0.910, which means > from 0.7. This shows that all indicators have consistency in measuring Repurchase Intention. If all indicators have been proven valid and reliable, then the next step is to measure the Inner Model.

B. Evaluation of Structural Models

R-Square Value

Service Quality and Marketing Mix variable has R-Square value of Customer Satisfaction, with the value of 0.809. This means Service Quality and Marketing mix has 80.9% influence on Customer Satisfaction and indicate that a relationship between dependent variable and independent variable is strong. However, Customer Satisfaction has R-Square value of Repurchase Intention with the value of 0.479. This means Customer Satisfaction only influence 47.9% to Repurchase Intention and indicate that the model is moderate.

Q-Square Evaluation

A Q-square value greater than 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance which of each endogenous variable in this study can be seen in the following calculation. The predictive-relevance value is obtained by the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R21) \times (1 - R22) \\ &= 1 - [(1 - 0.809) \times (1 - 0.479)] \\ &= 1 - (0.191 \times 0.521) \\ &= 1 - 0.099 \\ &= 0.901 \end{aligned}$$

The calculation results above show a predictive-relevance value of 0.901 (> 0). Thus, the model has a good predictive relevance value with combination amount 90.1%.

F² Evaluation

Based on F² Evaluation, the effect of Customer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention and Marketing Mix on Customer Satisfaction has a strong size effect value with a range of F Square values above 0.35. However, the Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction on has a weak size effect value with a range of F Square values between 0.02 and 0.15.

C. Hypothesis Testing

In the hypothesis testing, the estimated value for the path relationship in the structural model must be significant. This significance value can be obtained by bootstrapping procedure. Seeing the significance of the hypothesis by looking at the parameter coefficient value and the significance value of the T-statistic in the bootstrapping report.

Table 2. Hypothesis Testing

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CS -> RI	0.692	0.691	0.068	10.199	0.000
MM -> CS	0.780	0.749	0.103	7.600	0.000
SQ -> CS	0.139	0.167	0.102	1.365	0.086
SQ -> CS -> RI	0.096	0.120	0.079	1.221	0,111
MM -> CS -> RI	0.539	0.514	0.062	8.694	0.000

1. Testing the Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

The first hypothesis in the study is proven irrelevant, supported by the results of data analysis, revealing a p value of 0.086, which exceeds the conventional significance level of 0.05. Additionally, the t value of 1.365 lower than 1.96, further supports the lack of statistical significance in the relationship between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction. The path coefficient value of 0.139 underscores a minimal effect in the direction of the relationship. These findings show that in the context of the coffee shop under study, service quality does not have a significant impact on customer satisfaction. This finding emphasizes the importance of understanding the specific dynamics of the coffee industry and tailoring strategies to meet the unique expectations and preferences of the target consumer base.

2. Testing the Effect of Marketing Mix on Customer Loyalty

The affirmation of the second hypothesis in this study highlights the central role of the marketing mix in the shaping of customer satisfaction in the context of a coffee shop. Strong statistical evidence from data analysis supports this conclusion. The t-value of 7.600, which exceeds the critical threshold of 1.96, combined with a remarkably low p-value of 0.000 (below the widely accepted significance level of 0.05), provides a solid basis for asserting the statistical significance of the relationship. Furthermore, the path coefficient of 0.780 not only demonstrates statistical strength, but also a strong positive relationship between marketing mix and customer satisfaction. The results of this study indicate that the use of an effective marketing mix in a coffee shop is associated with an increase in customer satisfaction. The positive impact on customer satisfaction increases customer repurchase intention.

3. Testing the Effect of Customer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention

The validation of the third hypothesis in this study aligns with robust statistical evidence, affirming the significance of Customer Satisfaction as a crucial variable influencing Repurchase Intention. The t value of 10.533, exceeding the critical threshold of 1.96, coupled with a remarkably low p value of 0.000 (below the conventional significance level of 0.05), unequivocally underscores the statistical strength of the relationship. The path coefficient value of 0.692 indicates a strong effect and positive relationship direction. That means that increasing customer satisfaction has an appreciable and positive impact on consumer repurchase intention, and the higher the level of customer satisfaction, the more it will increase the consumer's intention to repurchase the product offered. Thus, it can conclude that Customer Satisfaction is a variable that can be considered to form Repurchase Intention.

4. Testing the Effect of Service Quality on Repurchase Intention through Repurchase Intention

The fourth hypothesis in the study is proven irrelevant, it can be supported by hypothesis 1 which shown the irrelevancy between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction. Furthermore, the results of data analysis show that the p value of 0.111 or higher than 0.05 even the t value is 1.221 which is greater than 1.96. The path coefficient value of 0.096 underscores a minimal effect in the direction of the relationship, implying that Service Quality holds no substantial influence on Repurchase Intention through the mediating factor of Customer Satisfaction. In light of these comprehensive analyses, it can be confidently concluded that the fourth hypothesis is indeed irrelevant, reinforcing the argument against the influence of Service Quality on Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction.

5. Testing the Effect of Marketing Mix on Repurchase Intention through Repurchase Intention

The validation of the fifth hypothesis underscores the significant impact of Marketing Mix on Repurchase Intention through the mediating factor of Customer Satisfaction. The robust statistical evidence, as indicated by the t value of 8.694 surpassing the critical threshold of 1.96, coupled with a highly significant p value of 0.000 (below the conventional significance level of 0.05), lends strong support to the assertion that Marketing Mix plays a crucial role in shaping Repurchase Intention.

CONCLUSION

In today's customer perspective, service quality may be considered commonplace for a coffee shop to implement because that is the way it should be. Therefore, in the case of Perihal Kopi, more attention is needed on developing marketing strategies that have proven to be effective and have a significant correlation with customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. There should be more intensive development of marketing activities. These steps must be taken on an ongoing basis to ensure that Perihal Kopi not only maintains its position in the market, but also continues to improve its competitiveness and win over customers. Based on the PLS-SEM analysis and the questionnaire regarding customer analysis at Perihal Kopi, answering the hypothesis test which presents a new perspective of customers, where service quality does not significantly affect customer satisfaction, marketing mix significantly affects customer satisfaction, customer satisfaction does significantly influences repurchase intention, service quality does not significantly influences repurchase intention through customer satisfaction, and marketing mix does significantly influence on repurchase intention through customer satisfactions.

RECOMMENDATION

Perihal Kopi may improve its 7P marketing mix to maintain its current customer and gain the prospect customer. In this study, there are any limitations remain so that the future study that could be conducted for Perihal Kopi could focus efforts on understanding more about the psychological factors that underlie consumer preferences and purchasing decisions in the context of coffee, especially in Depok. Perihal Kopi can also explore more about motivation, taste perception, and flavour that will help Perihal Kopi can have better understanding for the elements that have a major influence on consumer choice. To ensure that the strategy is implemented effectively and efficiently, Perihal Kopi's management may also seek assistance from third-party marketing professionals.

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